

Performance of CR1009 in multilocation trials

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CR1009 (Pankaj/Jagannath) is a promising, long-duration semidwarf cultivar that was developed at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack. It has good tillering capacity and produces short, bold, white grains.

CR1009 performance was compared with that of CO 25, also a long-duration variety, in samba (Aug-Feb) in multi-

Performance of CR1009 in multilocation trials at Chingleput, Tamil Nadu, India.

	Peruvoyal		Perittivakkam		Sivapuram	
	CR1009	CO 25	CR1009	CO 25	CR1009	CO 25
Sowing date	27 Aug 1982		03 Sep 1982		14 Sep 1982	
Planting date	28 Oct 1982		25 Oct 1982		31 Oct 1982	
Duration (days)	180	180	165	165	169	169
Grain yield (t/ha)	4.6	3.9	4.0	2.7	4.1	3.4
% increase over CO 25	17.6		49.1		21.8	
Ht at maturity (cm)	59	112	84	135	64	114
Productive tillers/m ²	915	175	990	805	680	520
Panicle length (cm)	16.3	18.5	17.5	19.1	18.9	17.9
Grains (no.)/panicle	61	64	62	72	67	71
1000-grain wt (g)	19.0	21.0	19.7	16.4	21.5	20.0

location trials in Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu. At 3 sites, CR1009 had from 17.6 to 49.1% higher grain yield than

CO 25 (see table). Crop duration ranged from 165 to 180 days. □

Mashuri vs local varieties on Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam

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Much of the Cuu Long River Delta (Vietnamese part of the Mekong Delta) is planted to late-maturing local varieties

with yields of 1.5 to 4 t/ha. At RRI, we have identified some modern varieties that can be grown successfully on the Delta.

We compared Mashuri, introduced in the 1980 IRTP nursery, to popular local varieties Trang Chum, Trang Lun, Tieu Doi, and Nang Huong. Mashuri yields in 3 consecutive years were encouraging (Table 1). Mashuri had shorter duration, more grains/panicle, lodging resistance,

wide adaptability, and good grain quality compared with local varieties.

Mashuri, Trang Chum, and Trang Lun are susceptible to brown planthopper and sheath blight and have resistance to leaf blast and bacterial leaf blight (Table 2). Mashuri is expected to withstand most pest attacks during the growing season.

Provincial agriculture departments and RRI are implementing large-scale seed multiplication programs. □

Table 1. Characteristics and yield of Mashuri and local varieties grown on the Cuu Long Delta.

Variety	Characteristic	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	Lodging (0-9)	Yield ^a (t/ha)		
							1980	1981	1982
Mashuri		150	132	264	230	3	3.7 a	4.0 a	5.4 a
Trang Lun	Acid sulfate tolerance	190	148	247	86	4	3.1 b	3.8 a	5.5 a
Trang Chum	Deepwater	180	137	204	124	5	3.1 b	3.7 a	—
Tieu Doi	Salinity tolerance	176	116	192	152	7	—	—	5.0 a
Nang Huong	Good quality	173	157	145	107	9	—	—	2.1 b

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at 5% level.

Table 2. Reaction of Mashuri to rice insects and diseases on Cuu Long Delta.^a

Variety	Brown planthopper (BPH)		Leaf blast (B1)		Bacterial leaf blight (BLB)		Sheath blight (ShB)	
	Infested (%)	Reaction	Scale (0-9)	Reaction	Scale (0.9)	Reaction	Scale (0-9)	Reaction
Mashuri	88	HS	2-6	R-MS	4	MS	9	HS
Trang Lun	85	HS	4-5	MS	3	MR	7	S
Trang Chum	85	HS	4-6	MS	3	MR	7	S
Resistant ^b	26	MR	1	R	1	R	7	S
Susceptible ^b	100	HS	4-9	MS-HS	8	S	9	HS

^aArtificial infestation, using IRRI test and scoring procedures. R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible. ^bResistant check for BPH = IR36, B1 = Tetep, BLB = Cempo Selak, ShB = IET4699. Susceptible check for BPH = TN1, B1 = NN7A, BLB = IR8, ShB = IR36.